

MOBILIZING YOUTH- CHALLENGES AND INITIATIVES UNDERTAKEN

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Abstract

The prospect of a society is dependent upon the dispositional behaviour of its Youth. The future of a community largely depends on where their youth are heading? What are they ideating? What decisions are they making for themselves? The decisions made by the young people regarding their educational and professional career affect the overall economic development of a society. They also have the responsibility to understand the problems faced by their communities and generate ideas to cater to the needs of the general public. Hence provision of such facilities for the people is required that will help them learn about their social environment, their area of interests, develop new ways of thinking and flourish resourcefulness. Mobilizing young people towards acquiring knowledge and skills will help create an impact on the socio-economic environment. Further, effective learning will assist in innovation and generation of sustainable solutions for socio-economic progress. Mobilization furnishes a smooth transition of young people towards exploring and capitalizing their strengths. It includes provision of opportunities to learn, research and collaborate. It also emphasizes assisting individuals towards gaining leadership potential, so they can help in redeveloping social engagement.

In India, involvement of parents and friends holds equal importance as equal importance is given to personal relationship building.

Aim of Paper

In this research paper we will discuss Skill India Mission, employability, schemes and initiatives started by government of India to enhance skill development and employment opportunities for youth and will identify the challenges which are required to be fulfilled for the purpose of skills employment and thereby helping India to become a developed country by 2047. The paper will also look into the skilling and entrepreneurship landscape of India.

Key Words: Mobilization of youth, UNESCO, Youth Bulge, skill- gap, Skill India

The potential of any society is dependent upon the inherent behaviour of its Youth. The future of a community largely depends on the direction in which their youth are heading, the ideas they are developing, and the decisions they are making for themselves. The decisions made by the young people regarding their educational and professional career affect the overall economic development of a society. They also have the responsibility to understand the problems faced by their communities and generate ideas to cater to the needs of the general public. Therefore, it becomes essential that the educational institutes, community leaders, and

local organizations are focusing on imparting knowledge about their social environment to the youth, helping them understand their role, explore new opportunities, making informed decisions and contribute to positive change. Mobilizing young people towards acquiring knowledge and skills will help create an impact on socio-economic environment. This way, effective learning among young individuals will assist in innovation and generation of sustainable solutions for socio-economic progress. Mobilization furnishes a smooth transition of young people towards exploring and capitalizing their strengths. It includes provision of opportunities to learn, research and collaborate. It also emphasizes on assisting individuals towards gaining leadership potential, so they can help in redeveloping social engagement. In India, along with the awareness level of these individuals, involvement of parents and friends holds equal importance in influencing the mobilization process. During mobilization an equal importance should be placed on personal relationship building and counselling of parents together with the targeted audience. Effective mobilization also needs improved awareness campaigns & faith-based marketing through local influencers to reach the masses. Today, our country has a “demographic advantage” in the form of youth surge, if we are able to utilize their full potential, we can move towards a sustained economic growth. In India, working in this direction, several initiatives and programmes have been upgraded and launched by the government and the private sector. These both have made significant efforts towards generating awareness among people for skill enhancement, entrepreneurship and community development. These initiatives work as supportive engines to ease out the mobilization process of developing youth in Indian society. Following paper highlights different challenges and barriers in mobilizing youth towards empowerment. Further, the paper also tries to provide a concise study on some of the programmes and initiatives launched by the government and private companies for the purpose youth transition, together with assessing the level of impact each one of them has created in developing vocational skills among young people and enabling them to avail gainful employment opportunities.

Introduction- It is necessary that youth of a society have accurate understanding of their ability, interests and skills. By utilizing their time and knowledge in learning and researching, these people can generate sustainable solutions. Along with this, having training facilities in their field of interest makes them acquire expertise, which help in bringing fresh perspectives on the table for different societal concerns. These ideas can be a major means for social reform. The future of a society is totally dependent upon decisions made by its young people with regard to their learning and development. A very urgent need to propel the youth generation towards sustainable decision making is felt because their decision patterns now will impact how a country’s future is shaped.

Mobilization refers to moving and arranging things in a set order to achieve predetermined objectives. According to UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization), Mobilization of youth refers to the process of empowering youth by making all required resources for learning available to them and helping them to achieve understanding of their actions and its outcomes. This

whole learning will decide their socio-economic progress. This process also involves initiating & motivating young people-led social reform movements that will generate a positive community impact.¹

Many globally led youth mobilization programmes are working towards helping individuals achieve training in skills that satisfy their interests and boost their knowledge. This will pave the pathway to economic opportunities for the people and will also lead them to take community actions. **Generation Unlimited** initiated by UNICEF (United Nations Children's Fund) is one such programme which is a public-private and youth partnership programme focusing on empowering youths with progressive opportunities and collaborating with them to address issues within their community.² Since its launch in 2018 by the UN Secretary-General, Generation Unlimited or GenU has worked towards encouraging innovation and entrepreneurship among young people along with providing them with technical knowledge. Global youth mobilization movement is aimed towards assisting people in effectively utilizing their cognition and foster empowerment. Several entrepreneurial opportunities are being designed at national and global level to cultivate engagement in citizens.

Effective mobilization starts with detailed research on the demographic and socio-economic environment of different concerned areas where developmental and employment opportunities are limited. This step is necessary to understand the population mix, present employment opportunities and the socio-economic challenges of the territory. Next, it requires development of skill building and training facilities for people in such areas, to provide them with consistent learning and employment opportunities. The next step is to have a group of people who can establish local connections with the community i.e. advertise about the means of learning accessible to them and bring awareness. Through this young people can be familiarized with opportunities accessible to them. After getting enrolled, they can work on building their abilities and secure their economic standing.

With the help of impactful mobilization programmes people can be developed to be future leaders. The young people are led by enthusiasm to bring change in the status quo of society. They, when given the right direction, can voice out their thoughts on political issues, education affordability, sustainability, and gender and ethnic diversity. Hence, there is a need to enable a large number of people to discover their potential so that they voice out their opinions in every matter concerning ecological health of their society.

Challenges in Mobilization-

Statistics from the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) showcase that there are 1.2 billion young people around the world. This number showcases that young people make up around 16 percent of the total population, the definition of young people being those between the age of 15 to 24 years.³ However, according to India's National Youth Policy 2014 the youths are considered to be those who are between the age of 15 and 29 years.⁴ According to statistics provided by the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MoSPI) the average age of the Indian population

¹ <https://en.unesco.org/gap/priority-action-areas/youth#:~:text=Mass%20mobilisation%20of%20youth%20towards,and%20innovative%20solutions%20and%20alternatives>.

² <https://www.generationunlimited.org/who-we-are>

³ <https://www.un.org/en/global-issues/youth>

⁴ <https://yas.gov.in/sites/default/files/DRAFT%20NATIONAL%20YOUTH%20POLICY%2025july23>

is 29 years, which makes India to have one of the youngest populations in the world. The MoSPI addresses this increase of young population in India as “*Youth Bulge*”.⁵ This thing is also notable when there is a massive digital transformation and needs and views of people are changing for their future. A nation having an extensively rich youth population is considered to have an economically sustained future. Having a visibly strong demographic advantage of a large young population will help a country to achieve economic growth and experience a shift in their cultural and social setting. However, to gain this benefit, it is important that there is an active involvement of public policy makers, private organizations, local community heads to effectively engage and mobilize these youth towards achieving their full potential. And this can be achieved by taking into account the preferences of individuals and generating effective policies accordingly.

For a productive economy there is a necessity of every young mind to be able to develop new ideas and they be able to deliver services as a labour force. The younger a nation’s population, the better are the chances of it becoming progressive and developed, provided, there is a non- prohibited access of education, training and health facilities to them. The “Youth Bulge” in the Indian economy may face challenges such as limited access to educational resources, increased unemployment because of lack of skilled training, gender inequality, and having restricted knowledge related to health services. In mobilizing youth participation there is a need to reform policies and initiate programs that encourage youth learning and enable awareness at the local level. There are some elements which act as barrier or challenge for mobilization, which are-

1. Limited or no awareness among people especially those belonging to below poverty line about the available prospects for growth.
2. Non- efficiently trained counsellors, make student attrition rate high as the students are not able to visualize benefits, they will be getting after getting enrolled with a training institute.
3. Inefficient understanding of “skill- gap”. There is a need for real time skill gap assessment at local level which can help in efficiently arranging the required resources for training and development of individuals.
4. Having lack of research on demographic and socio-economic diversity, make it difficult to identify and relate opportunities available to the population of that district.
5. No local connections or relations of training institutes with the community heads, local leaders and administrative bodies make it difficult to outreach the community people and generate regional recognition.
6. Parents are very much involved in decision making for a child’s future especially when girl students are concerned. There is incompetence on part of training institutes to provide assistance to parents on proposed benefits of formal training and migration.

⁵ <https://www.mospi.gov.in/publication/youth-india-2022>

Focus on Youth: Indian Perspective

The Indian government has always focused on developing and harnessing the potential of youth of India, for which several developmental initiatives such as National Cadet Corps (NCC), National Service Scheme (NSS), Nehru Yuva Kendra Sangathan (NYKS) etc were undertaken. However, the recent changes in the direction of development of youth potential is also notable. The National Youth Policy 2014 focuses on engaging youth in up-skilling and re-skilling themselves, also the current focus is on youth digital inclusion, to grow their learning network. Further, the goal of National Youth Policy is to partner along with the various community stakeholders to reach out to the youth, to strengthen educational institutes for encouraging young people towards developing analytical capabilities and fostering creativity.

In this direction, Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi had launched the “*Skill India*” mission on 15 July, 2015,⁶ to emphasize upon the need of harnessing the potential of youth surge in India. He specially focused on the idea that global challenges can be tackled with careful planning and implementation of policies that focuses on skilling and enabling youth of India.⁷

The MSDE (Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship) is motivated towards Skill enhancement across the country, which involves meeting the demand of the current skilled jobs by ensuring efficient supply of skilled workforce. The MSDE focuses on providing vocational and technical training with the help of its aided hands like Directorate General of Training (DGT), NCVET (National Council for Vocational Education and Training), NSDC (National Skill Development Corporation), National Skill Development Fund (NSDF) and about 15000 ITIs (Industrial Training Institutes). Skill development is the collective responsibility of central, state governments, NGOs, international organizations, community-based organizations and the corporate sector as well. Collaborative efforts from these stakeholders can bring effective mass mobilization of youth towards development.

The Annual Report 2023-24 of Ministry of Skill Development & Entrepreneurship highlights that annually, over one crore young individuals under Skill India mission have gained essential skills to secure improved livelihood.

Speaking on the effectiveness of various schemes under Skill India initiative, Mr. Jayant Singh Chaudhary, The Minister of State (Independent Charge) in MSDE, also stated that “as per a survey conducted by *Indian Institute of Public Administration (IIPA)*, 70.5% of surveyed candidates under PMKVY (Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana) have received placement in their desired skill sector. Further, a separate third-party evaluation for Jan Shikshan Sansthan (JSS) scheme showcases that 77.05% of trainees have gone through gainful professional changes. As highlighted in a Tracer Study of ITI graduates, 63.5% of ITI graduates got employment, out of which 6.7% of the pass-outs were self-employed.”

Entrepreneurship and Skill Development Programmes (ESDP) is focused on providing skills to the young people who are eager for self-employment and are motivated to establish their own business. Under this program several activities related to encouraging self-employment are being organized in several

⁶<https://www.msde.gov.in/en/about-msde/background#:~:text=The%20Skill%20Mission%20launched%20by,for%20Skill%20Development%20and%20Entrepreneurship>

⁷ <https://www.narendramodi.in/mobile/pm-s-remarks-at-the-launch-of-skill-india->

business schools and technical institutions. The main objective behind launching this initiative is to encourage the young people in India towards entrepreneurship and motivate them to adopt self-employment as a career option. This scheme comes under the purview of Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME). Under this scheme 4 types of activities or programs are included, which are- Entrepreneurship-cum-Skill Development Programme(E-SDP), Management Development Programme (MDP), Entrepreneurship Awareness Programme (EAP) and Industrial Motivational Campaign. To ensure women's mobility into self- business, the program ensures that 40% of the participants in EAP and E-SDP are women.

A detailed report on number of various programmes designed and executed within the framework of this scheme is provided by the Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME). The report highlights that from financial year 2018-19 to financial year 2024-25, a total of 31,845 programmes have been implemented, under which 14,50,906 individuals have gained benefits.

Number of Programmes launched under ESDP in each financial year

Source: Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

Number of beneficiaries of various ESDP programmes in each financial year

Source: Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

Top 10 state-wise no. of programmes launched under ESDP in FY 2024-2025

Source: Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

Top 10 state-wise no. of beneficiaries of various ESDP programmes in FY 2024-2025

Source: Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

National Programme for Youth and Adolescent Development (NPYAD) is an umbrella scheme, operated by the Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports. This scheme is developed to cover all schemes working for the same goal of skill development, entrepreneurship, sports, and leadership programs. Mainly following 4 major schemes are included under NPYAD namely- Promotion of Youth Activities and Training, Promotion of National Integration, Nehru Yuva Kendra Sangathan- NYKS, and National Youth Corps- NYC. The goal of this scheme is to integrate youth towards social harmony, personality development, leadership development, risk-taking and team collaboration, to make them ready for any

situation and challenge. Further this scheme also aims to foster zeal to work for national progression among the young and adolescent population.⁸ With the help of National Youth Festivals, Awards, Exchange programmes, leadership and training development, the NPYAD is working towards creating and developing future leaders for the country. Along with this, this programme is developed to benefit all the candidates, who are either members of groups affiliated to Nehru Yuva Kendra Sangathan, NSS (National Service Scheme), State Government Youth Organisations and Bharat Scouts & Guides, or are students in Schools, Colleges and Universities or are adolescents and youth from other established youth organizations and NGOs. These candidates are given counselling, career guidance and skill education, so that they can shape their careers accordingly. Several seminars, workshops and conferences are being organized under this programme to address prevailing community concerns and further nurture research to tackle such issues. This scheme covers people in the age group of 13 to 35 years (called 'youth') and 10-19 years (called 'adolescent' under the scheme).⁹

Under Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDU-GKY), which is a part of Aajeevika- the Mission for poverty reduction, the aim is to identify rural poor youth of India and impart industry related skills and knowledge to them. Further provide them with employment solutions that provide regular wages. These projects are taken as Single State Projects providing each state with full ownership on DDU-GKY projects in their state. These projects are specially focused on not only providing training but also focus on career progression of the people enrolled, by providing employment opportunities.¹⁰ Together with this, counselling of youth is done along with their parents to ease out the mobilization process. The person wanting to enrol in this programme can reach out to their Gram Panchayat who will further assist that person to the nearest training centre. People enrolled in this scheme will get one to one counselling on the basis of their aptitude and area of interest. This initiative is backed by an authorized certificate given by the government and helps in building a network with potential employers; for grabbing placement opportunities that pay at least Rs. 6000/- per month.¹¹ For implementation of DDU-GKY initiative, the age group of target poor rural youth is decided to be in between 15-35, with a relaxation of 10 years in upper-age limit for women, Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs), Person with Disabilities (PwDs), Transgender and other special groups. Here, the identification of poor people will be done through a process namely Participatory Identification of Poor (PIP).

As per the report published by Ministry of Rural Development (MoRD) on Dec 2024, a total of 16,90,046 candidates have been trained under DDU-GKY till Nov 2024, out of which 10,97,265 candidates were successful in securing a gainful livelihood.¹² This accounts for 65% of the total trained population from year 2014-15 to Nov 2024.

Following is the data provided by MoRD on the number of candidates trained and employed in top 15 sectors under the scheme.

⁸ <https://yas.nic.in/sites/default/files/NPYAD%20Scheme%20Guidelines%202014-15>

⁹ <https://nyks.nic.in/schemes/NPYAD-Guidelines.pdf>

¹⁰ <https://www.india.gov.in/spotlight/deen-dayal-upadhyaya-grameen-kaushalya-yojana>

¹¹ <https://static.pib.gov.in/WriteReadData/specificdocs/documents/2022/jan/doc2022163601>

¹² <https://rural.gov.in/en/press-release/beneficiaries-under-deen-dayal-upadhyaya-grameen-kaushalya-yojana-ddu-gky>

Total number of candidates trained and placed in top 15 sectors under DDU-GKY

Source: Beneficiaries under Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana - DDU-GKY, Ministry of Rural Development

As per the guidelines of DDU-GKY, at the national level, 50% of the total funds of the program is to be allocated for skill development of Scheduled Casts (SCs) & Scheduled Tribes (STs). This ensures that these communities have equal access to development opportunities under the scheme. Further, it is also required that to ensure inclusiveness, each state must ensure that at least 33% of the beneficiaries receiving benefits under the scheme should be women, 15% should be minorities, and 5% should be PwD (Persons with Disabilities) candidates. Following chart depicts the number of women, SC, ST and PwD candidates trained and placed from year 2021-22 to 2023-24 and 2024-25 till Nov'24.

Total number of SC,ST and PwD women candidates trained and placed under DDU-GKY

Source: Beneficiaries under Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana - DDU-GKY, Ministry of Rural Development

PMKVY (Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana) is aimed to provide employment opportunities to people who are less educated or have left education for any reason, by providing them with training in essential skills for performing any job or starting their own business. Hence this scheme is focused on enabling and mobilizing youth to develop themselves for achieving sustainable livelihood and work for economic growth of India. The age group to be benefitted from this scheme will be of age between 15 to 45 years. The scheme provides courses for ability building of the people. Three categories of courses are provided under this programme which includes courses for non-literate or unskilled people who want to get employed but do not have essential skills to earn a livelihood (Short Term Training, STT), courses for skilled people to upgrade them for dynamic transformations and assess themselves & get certified (Recognition of Prior Learning, RPL), third type of training is for people belonging to marginalized, unprivileged and remotely located geographical section of society. This type of training is delivered outside affiliated training centres, to fulfil the contemporary potential skill needs of these people.¹³ PMKVY scheme was implemented in the year 2015. Since then, this scheme has been relaunched, with each iteration reflecting minor shifts in its objectives.

- Under PMKVY 1.0 (2015-16) scheme 19.86 lakh candidates were trained.
- For PMKVY 2.0 & PMKVY 3.0 data is being hereby provided.

¹³ https://www.pmkvyofficial.org/photos/General_document/PMKVY%204.0%20Guidelines

PMKVY 2.0 (2016-2020)		
Component	Certified	Placed
Centrally Sponsored Centrally Managed Component	84,82,187	19,07,919
Centrally Sponsored State Managed Component	6,56,478	2,24,796
Total	91,38,665	21,32,715
People Certified and Placed Under STT	27,70,000	15,32,000

Source: <https://skillsip.nsdscindia.org/>

Chart showcases the percentage of candidates placed among those who were certified.

Source: <https://skillsip.nsdscindia.org/>

PMKVY 3.0 (2020-22)		
Component	Certified	Placed
Centrally Sponsored Centrally Managed Component	3,02,572	22,643
Centrally Sponsored State Managed Component	97,288	7,956
Total	3,99,860	30,599
People Certified and Placed Under STT	1,12,000	30,599

Source: <https://eparlib.nic.in/> and <https://www.business-standard.com/>

PMKVY 4.0 is currently being implemented FY 2022-26 to mitigate existing challenges of “Skill India Programme’ scheme. The focus will primarily be on reinforcing existing skill and education ecosystem while meeting emerging needs of the society. The objective of PMKVY 4.0 is to deliver market-oriented skills to the youth, enhance access to skilling via technology and digitalization and link marginalized communities and the people residing in remote areas to the prevalent skill ecosystem.¹⁴

YuWaah initiative introduced by the Minister of Women and Child Development, Mrs. Smriti Irani is a part of the public-private and society partnership programme of UNICEF called **Generation Unlimited (GenU)**. This programme aims towards enhancing foundational, vocational, transferable and life skill knowledge of the young people aged between 10 to 24 years,¹⁵ to successfully prepare them for employment opportunities. Further, the aim of this initiative is to strengthen the educational facilities in the country to equip young minds with creative and critical thinking, to encourage the spirit of research, idea generation and entrepreneurship. Additionally, the youth is encouraged to start and support community projects to confront societal issues and bring positive social impact.

Under YuWaah, several initiatives such as Passport to Earning (P2E), FunDoo program, Step Up – Bano Job Ready and UPSHIFT have been introduced, to sensitize youth on 21st century skills thereby enhancing their employability and linking them to relevant job opportunities.

In today’s evolving era, it is essential that everyone can access quality digital education to thrive in the rapidly changing world of work. Emergence of new technology pose a significant challenge on the learners to keep up with the pace of rapid development and succeed in making a stable livelihood. Passport to Earning or P2E is a digital platform that aims to provide free, job-relevant digital learning to people aged between 15 to 24 years, to enable them acquire employment ready skills and connect them with various job opportunities. P2E solution runs on Microsoft Community Training (MCT) platform to connect young people with quality coaching, mentoring and apprenticeships. As of July 2024, P2E has certified 2 million young people with digital and financial skills in India.¹⁶ FunDoo is a chat-based solution, initially launched in India by UNICEF and YuWaah to overcome insufficient awareness around Covid-19 vaccination among people, to provide them with reliable medical and health related information and help them make informed decisions. It now provides digital coaching on 21st century skilling, employability, green skills, career development and a range of information on climate change, gender-based violence, mental health, immunization and much more. It is designed to work even on low-bandwidth. According to a UNICEF, India article published in April 2024, this initiative has got 948,000 successful registrations, since its launch in 2020, where 56.5% of the users are male, 39.3% are female, 0.6% are other, and 3.6% are unknown.¹⁷

¹⁴ <https://www.ibef.org/government-schemes/pradhan-mantri-kaushal-vikas-yojana>

¹⁵ <https://yuwaah.org/>

¹⁶ <https://www.generationunlimited.org/passport-earning-p2e#:~:text=In%20India%2C%20Passport%20to%20Earning,country%20in%20its%20first%20year.>

¹⁷ <https://www.unicef.org/india/stories/fundoo-way-upskill-yourself-future-0>

Chart: Gender wise segregation of the total registration on FunDoo solution

Step Up programme helps job seekers develop soft skills, build resume, understand job application processes and explore upskilling opportunities. This enables young people to connect with the relevant job opportunities on various private and government job portals. This programme also facilitates support to the people in segregating reliable and genuine job opportunities from the fake ones. By 2024, this initiative of YuWaah has supported over 1 million young people in connecting with jobs.¹⁸

UPSHIFT focuses on developing entrepreneurial mindset among young people of the country. This programme includes workshops, mentorships and experimental learning facilities to build skills and opportunities for people facing disadvantages. Participants in this programme learn to develop essential abilities in areas like critical thinking, creativity, problem solving, digital literacy, communication and collaboration (often referred as 21st century skills). This enables young people to analyse and understand community challenges, identify opportunities, and innovate products and services to address these adversities. In India, first UPSHIFT pilot was done with 60 students in 2019 in Andhra Pradesh. According to an article by UNICEF, in June 2024, “UPSHIFT from a 60-student pilot in India has now expanded to cover over 430,000 students in almost 19,000 schools in 4 states namely Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Telangana. Along with this, 10,000 Atal Tinkering Labs have also been established across the country to support innovative and entrepreneurial mindset in the youth.”¹⁹

¹⁸ <https://www.unicef.org/india/employment-opportunities-young-people>

¹⁹ <https://www.unicef.org/innovation/stories/india-innovator-every-household#:~:text=The%20skills%2Dbuilding%20programme%20is,and%20practice%2021st%2Dcentury%20skills.>

Chart: Total no. of young people skilled through UPSHIFT

Source: Scaling UPSHIFT into Education Systems, UNICEF Report, September 2023 and UNICEF Innovation Article, June 2024

Chart: Number and percentage of schools implementing UPSHIFT by state

Source: Scaling UPSHIFT into Education Systems, UNICEF Report, September 2023

Impact created by YuWaah with its network of partners in India-

Chart: Number of young individuals empowered by YuWaah nationwide (numbers in millions) (2019- 2024) Source: Generation Unlimited Article {YuWaah (GenU India)}

The United Nations Development Programme along with India Development Foundation has started a programme called Disha which aims to support underprivileged women in India to gain employment through employment enabled training, marketable skills and entrepreneurial skill development opportunities.

Private organizations like Tata and Ambuja Cement are also involved in facilitating services for youth development. Initiatives like Tata Strive and Ambuja Cement Foundation are prime examples of collaboration of private organizations with the youth body of India to cultivate knowledge roots among them to strive for an economically strong future.

Tata Strive is a community service initiative which is focused on providing soft skills, authentic certifications, and ensuring quality skill assessment. This initiative was launched by the Tata Sons Private Limited in the year 2014. This is a project which focuses on identifying industry trends and understanding technological innovations and trying to provide training to the students in different domains. The courses provided are essentially relevant to real time industrial applications and provide on the job training to the candidates. Different industry requirement-based skill certification courses are provided on this platform which can be opted by the individual on the basis of their own interests. All certifications are based on industry standards and provide audio-visual aids that help people understand the jobs to which they are showing interest.

The company has highlighted the impact of this initiative on the official website of Tata Strive. Based on the FY 2024 data, Tata Strive is working towards skilling youth from underprivileged backgrounds and as a result 64.75% of the individuals have gained successful placement in various employment positions. Further 12% of the candidates have successfully started and are running their own businesses. These all individuals have been able to maintain an average salary of Rs. 13,697.82 as a result of this initiative. Apart from this, it is notable that 70% of the learners in the community initiative are below 12th standard, wherein 27% of the candidates are women and 54% of the candidates belong to SC/ST and OBC

community. This highlights the inclusiveness of training programmes under Tata Strive, where people regardless of their background and identity are able to equally access and avail developmental opportunities and contribute towards more harmonious and developed societies. In the Annual Report of Tata Strive for year 2023-24, impact created by various initiatives under the project have been highlighted. Following data represents level of impact created by the project from 31st July 2014 to 31st Mach 2024, in providing jobs, enhancing employability, career counselling and skill development.

Chart: Total Beneficiaries of Tata Strive initiative from year 2014 to 2024, The percentage for SC, ST & OBC and women candidates are shown (Source: Annual Report Tata Strive 2023-24)

Ambuja Cement Foundation (ACF) provides training to the people on the basis of their interest in a particular field, in their training centres. They provide counselling to the young people and their parents at the time of training and at the time of job placement as well. This mentoring at every level makes them settle on their jobs and thus ease out the mobilization while also focusing on quality placement opportunities. According to the data provided by Ambuja Foundation on their official website, ACF’s SEDI (Skill & Entrepreneurship Development Institute) program has given training to over 1,00,000 rural youth since its inception. SEDI provides relevant training & skill courses in various sectors of electronics, IT, ITes, construction, health and hospitality etc. to help rural youth overcome unemployment. So far, the Skill & Entrepreneurship Development Institute program has been successful in employing 75% of its total trainees in valuable job positions, 25,000 of the trainees have been able to innovate and start their own businesses. Further, SEDI empowers girls and boys to take up on courses of their interests. If girls want to join courses in machine operation, electrical and welding and boys wants to join beautician and nursing courses, they are strongly encouraged by the program team members, rather than suppressing their interests because of

existing “gender stereotypes”. Till date, 1610 girls and 1840 boys have been successfully trained and guided by the SEDI team in such courses, effectively encouraging gender equality among people.²⁰

Conclusion-

In conclusion, to bring radical improvement in the society and develop innovation and critical thinking among young people, several initiatives have been launched by the government and private sector in India. The various government initiatives as above mentioned include Skill India programme under Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurship and Skill Development Programmes (ESDP), National Programme for Youth and Adolescent Development (NPYAD), Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDU-GKY), PMKVY (Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana) and the public-private and society partnership programme YuWaah. These programmes have consistently worked towards generating awareness for skill enhancement among people. Further, the initiatives have also contributed towards generating a skilled workforce that can match with the requirements of the current employment opportunities, by providing required vocational, technical and on-the-job training and certifications to the young people. These schemes have recorded a notable impact, with thousands of people getting trained in relevant skills and subsequently gaining placements in various sectors. Several people have also been able to innovate and start their own businesses as a part of different entrepreneurial training programs. Above all, most of the entrepreneurs are either from rural backgrounds or are young individuals studying in schools and colleges. However, there are limited interventions from the side of government to understand and reduce the gap between people gaining certifications and those getting placed. Further, private sector initiatives such as Tata Strive and Ambuja Cement Foundation (ACF) are also working towards enhancing employability and creating career awareness among young individuals. They have also been able to provide secured and improved livelihood to the marginalized communities. By encouraging and ensuring active participation of each individual regardless of their background and identity, Tata Strive has successfully worked towards improving social inclusion. In this series, to break “gender stereotypes”, ACF’s SEDI has also encouraged young girls and boys to take up courses of their choice, whether or not these courses belong to the prespecified gendered-criteria. Though collective initiatives from both government and private sector have created a remarkable impact on the overall development of the young people, they need to maximize their efforts to reach more and more underprivileged people and communities. Continuous efforts from their side will help in harnessing the full potential of the Indian youth, ensuring a positive societal change and an economically sustainable tomorrow.

²⁰ <https://www.ambujafoundation.org/blog/1-00-000-youth-skilled-across-10-states-by-ambuja-foundation-s-sedi-initiative>

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